

Ambiguity in Understanding of Teachers and Students on Creative Method Effectiveness: A Study on Primary Schools in Bangladesh

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Bangladesh has been witnessing nearly 100% enrollment ratio in primary education over the past several years despite adverse environment. But a large number of children leave education after primary level and become victim of child labor. The Government of Bangladesh has recently introduced a creative method at primary level, keeping most of the teachers untrained. So, teachers depend on either guidebooks, available in local markets, or their self-thought and wisdom. According to the findings of this survey, 13% teachers have no complete understanding on creative method, 47% take help from guidebooks, and 25% think that creative method system is not suitable to primary students. Whereas 92% students rely on guidebooks, 67% students need help of private tutors, 25% students do not understand the question papers at exam halls, and 25% students see both mathematics and English most difficult to learn. This survey, thereby, easily reflects a real understanding on the scenario of primary education in Bangladesh.

Keywords: Primary school, primary education, creative method, teachers training.

Introduction

Primary education is the foundation of education for any nation. It conveys ins and outs of the basis of education in Bangladesh and fundamental roles of essentiality of education. Primary Education in Bangladesh has made a significant achievement for the last two decades, especially for girls and underprivileged children. The study bears significance of creative method of primary education and its status in Bangladesh. There are 16.4 million children (aged 6 to 10) who have already enrolled in the primary schools of Bangladesh. Net enrollment ratio was 90.8% in 2009 but the drop out ratio was also high. Only 50.7% students can complete primary level which lasts for five years. In addition, poor educational facilities are common at primary schools in Bangladesh. Student-teacher ratio was 60:1 in the 1990s, 58:1 in 2005, and 49:1 in 2009. So, the teacher-student ratio is getting better but quality education has not been ensured in recent years. There are some facts to consider: education quality is decreasing day by day, effectiveness of the “creative method” has nipped in the bud, and poor educational facilities are a major feature.

Objective

The objectives of the study are followings:

- To explore effectiveness of creative method of primary education in Bangladesh.

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- To investigate level of understanding both students and teachers of primary schools in Bangladesh.
- To explore major issues and effects of creative method of primary level in Bangladesh

Scope of the Study

Primary education possesses utmost importance in our national life. Primary education is the basis of building up a skilled citizenry and the path to include the whole population within the education system. So, equal opportunities will be created to ensure access of all sections of children to primary education irrespective of ethnicity, socio-economic conditions, physical or mental challenges and geographical differences. This is the Constitutional responsibility of the state. Since this stage forms the foundation of subsequent levels of education, so delivery of quality primary education is a must. And since many of the students seek employment after this stage, a strong base in primary education will equip them better in the job market. To strengthen the general foundation of primary education at the national level, the existing discriminations among schools in regard to facilities, infrastructure constraints, lack of adequate number of teachers and the weaknesses in training will be adequately addressed. Primary education will be universal, compulsory, free and of uniform quality for all. At present 100% children cannot be given access to primary schools for economic, regional and geographical factors. By 2010-11, 100% enrollment of primary education will be ensured. At least one primary school will be established in the villages that have none.

Research Method

Both qualitative as well as quantitative approaches have been used for analyzing the data and descriptive research design would be followed. Qualitative data is collected through questionnaire interviewing from two target group teachers and students (students of both class three and class five). Here for instance;

- 1) Teachers of primary schools
- 2) Students of class five and
- 3) Students of Class Three

In addition to, there are some observation is included within the study. Quantitative data has been obtained through formal interviewing questionnaire. Both open ended and close ended questions are formulated for teachers and students. The primary focus of the study is to level of understanding of the primary students at primary level. The study area is across the country Bangladesh.

The study is based on Primary; data. Primary sources of data collection refer to the original sources that the researcher was expected to rely on when conducting the research work or the study which will enable the researcher to produce the final report. It provides first-hand information although personal interviews, observations and also questionnaires. The primary data are collected from 20 primary schools, 16 districts, and five broad areas for instance; broader areas of Bangladesh, wetland, hill-track, district town and rural village etc.

The collected data have been accumulated, organized, tabulated and analyzed keeping in mind of research objectives. The analysis of both qualitative and quantitative data have been analyzed after coding of qualitative data and both qualitative data and quantitative data have been analyzed with the help of by using Microsoft Excel and SPSS (Statistical tool for Social Science), Minitab etc. Furthermore, different kinds of chart, picture and map have been included for enriching research report along with analyzing social realities, causalities and social phenomena.

Sample Size

We have total sample size of 1201 respondents across the country. These respondent are consisted of Class three, class five and 40 primary school teachers. Counts of them subsequently are-

Table-1

Number of Surveyed Respondents on the Group Basis

Groups	Respondents
Class Three Students	556
Class Five Students	605
Primary School Teacher	40
Total	1201

Limitations of the Study

For conducting the research paper we face some problems. These limitations are discussed below:

- We faced that teacher category respondent did not provide information as they thought it may hamper in activities. For that there was some constraints in co-ordination from teacher responsiveness.
- We have some financial constraints for conducting the survey.
- For our survey purpose, we took interview from primary level students. All of them are below 18 years. For that we faced some problems when we collected data from them.

Creative Education in Bangladesh

Education is the key to a nation's development. Education is the principal means to achieve the goal of poverty alleviation. A properly educated nation, which is modern in genius and intellect and forward-looking in thinking, can only put the country at the zenith of its development. To ensure this Ministry of Education (MoE) holds the responsibility of updating the education policy prepared earlier with some fixed objectives and finally implemented 'Education Policy-2010' which one is revised carefully considering creative learning process. Different question pattern than the previous traditional way is introduced to further facilitate the development of thinking ability, imaginative capability, inquisitiveness and creativity of the learners. The important aspect of this latest education policy is it emphasizes religion, science and technical education. This latest Education Policy-2010 has some notable characters that made learning more enjoyable but yet effective. The learners will be enabled to learn without relying on so-called note books and private tuitions which are considered as hindrance to creativity. Examination has to be held in a peaceful, secure and congenial environment; it will never become scaring for them, rather they will accept it as a joyful festivity. The examinees will welcome the examinations as an opportunity of evaluation and recognition of the success of their academic life. Comprehensive education will contribute to make life attractive, secure and joyful. Creation of such an environment is bearing too much significance to achieve.

It was the intention to observe forms of creativity and how it is successfully incorporate across the curriculum. The creative education method supports the benefits of creativity in engaging children in their learning and stimulating ideas for creative teaching. Being creative does not only involve the study of art, which is how it has been perceived through the years. Creativity is the use of the imagination to enable the user to explore ways of solving problems, enquiring and thinking about their work. Children may have preferred or natural learning styles, kinesthetic, auditory or visual. The benefits of creativity are

numerous. Raising children's self-esteem is a part of this education system. When being creative children are neither right nor wrong, many lessons have various outcomes depending on the culture and experiences of the children in the class. Major advantages of the creative education method are discussed below:

- Stimulates the intellectual and practical qualities of the learners so that moral, human, cultural, scientific and social values are established at personal and national levels;
- Fosters creative and thinking faculties among the learners through a system of education that contains indigenous spirit and elements and which will lead to a life oriented development of knowledge of the learners;
- Evolves an education process that is oriented to creativity, practicability and productivity to achieve advancement in the economic and social fields of the country;
- Creates a scientific mindset of the students and to develop in them the qualities of leadership;
- Ensures the marginal competencies of learners at each level so that they are discouraged from rote learning, rather use their own thoughtfulness, imagination and urge for curiosity;
- Ensures skills of high standard at different areas and levels of education so that learners can successfully compete at the global context;
- Attaches substantial importance to information and communication technology (ICT) along with math, science and English in order to build up a digital Bangladesh based on knowledge-orientation and cultivation of ICT;
- Puts special emphasis on the extension of education; gives priority to primary and secondary education; motivates the students to show dignity of labor; enables students to acquire skills in vocational education to facilitate self-employment, irrespective of levels of education;
- Ensures a creative, favorable and joyful environment for the students at the primary level for their proper protection and congenial development;
- Ensures proper quality of education at each level and correlates the competencies learnt at the earlier level (as per the aims and objectives of education) with the next one to consolidate the formations of knowledge and skills; promotes extension of such knowledge and skills; enables the learners to acquire these skills; motivates the people to participate in the educational process, in particular to realize the objectives of education;
- Extends the use of information and communication technology (ICT) instrumental in educational process at every level;
- Takes necessary steps to create facilities of playground, sports, games and physical exercises in all educational institutions for the healthy growth of the physical and mental qualities of the learners;
- Initiates special measures to promote education in the areas identified as backward in education.

Analysis and Findings

The study is conducted for creative method in primary education. It is mentioned that there are no training on creative method to the primary school teachers from the prescribed authority. In the study, there are two sections for instance; one for teachers and another for students. The first part is for teachers.

- From the survey, 13% teachers don't understand creative method; 45% teachers understand creative method; and 42% teachers have slight understanding. So, from the survey findings, more than half of total teachers don't understand creative method effectively. If the teachers don't have a clear understanding how they could teach the kids at primary level!

- From the survey, 47% teachers rely on guidebooks, available in local markets; 35% teachers discuss the method with colleague; and 18% teachers teach their students with their self-wisdom. About half of the total teachers take helps from guidebooks. No training will be provided by the government to primary teachers.
- From the survey, 25% teachers think creative method is not appropriate for primary school students, 20% teachers opine on modification into existing method. But 55% teachers think the method can somewhat work. So, it is clear that one-fourth of the total teachers cited that the system is not adjusted to student of the primary level.

There are four questions for the primary students. The following finding of the survey is:

- From the survey, 92% students take help of guidebooks. Only 8% students stay away from guidebook. So, students' dependency on guidebook is a major concern. They are not becoming 'creative' rather making themselves confined to the guidebooks.
- From the survey, 67% students take help of private tutor to understand creative method by students and 33% don't. So, two-third of students take help of private tutor in Bangladesh. So, primary education is turning into a tutor and coaching-based education.
- From the survey, 25% students don't understand questions paper at the examination center but 75% students understand question paper at the exam hall. So, one-fourth students don't understand the question papers at all.
- From the survey, 3% students see Bangla is difficult to learn, 39% students find English is most difficult, 33% students think that mathematics is most difficult whereas 25% students considers both mathematics and English here most difficult subjects to learn. So, it is easily perceivable that most of the students in Bangladesh face difficulties in both Mathematics and English subjects.

Recommendations

Teachers from primary schools across the Bangladesh recommend few terms to succeed creative method,

1. Specialized teachers training should be arranged
2. Specialized teachers should be recruited for each subject
3. Questions papers need to make easier
4. Digital equipment's such as projector, computer and internet need to arrange to school
5. Need extra supports to unprivileged schools in wetland, border and remote village and coastal areas.

Conclusion

Primary education is witnessing an increasing enrollment rate. But its effectiveness does not apparently bring the result as expected. Teachers and students have not been adapted to the "Creative Method" yet since the government introduced this method. Teachers in primary schools are not provided with adequate training on creative method. More or less, scenarios of the existing primary education across Bangladesh are the same. Time has come to think again whether we need to introduce any new method or reshuffle the existing primary education system, in order to ensure a better tomorrow for our children.

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